

23rd Panhellenic Academic Libraries Conference

“Academic Libraries: A roadmap to sustainability” 15-16 November 2017,
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki.

Twenty-third (23rd) edition of the Panhellenic Academic Library Conference celebrated for the first time in three years on November 15th-16th 2017 in Thessaloniki, presented a timely opportunity for recent projects stocktaking, especially focusing initiatives co-financed by consecutive Community Structural Funds and National Strategic Development Plans between years 1994 and 2013 that laid strong foundations for academic library infrastructural and HR competential upgrade encouraging at the same time the articulation of a cooperative innovation framework.

During the opening ceremony keynote address, Prof. Ariadni Stogiannidou, Vice Rector for Academic & Student Affairs and Mrs. Katerina Nasta, Head of Aristotle University Central Library and Conference Scientific Committee Chair briefly outlined current situation pain points revolving around the degree to which the economic downturn has impacted Greek Academic Libraries, both placing an emphasis on the

importance of

- cross-organizational co-operation,
- the necessity to embrace open science / open access new paradigms framed within the general effort to respond to pressures for librarian-researcher-academia collaboration intensification and finally
- a more dynamic library involvement in the Learning and Teaching process in a “Respect the past, create the future” inspirational approach that brought to mind Gorman’s reformulation of Ranganathan’s 5th Law.

As to the event agenda, there were four modular sessions on each of the two conference days, six of which were open access, academic library cooperatives, institutional repositories, InfoLit and librarian Continuing Professional Development (CPD), library automation integrated systems and federated search, Altmetrics and research evaluation oriented while the last two components offered us valuable insights to European Documentation Centers communication channels, visual literacy and library space design projects and Wikidata/library potential collaboration.

Thanks to the University’s Research Dissemination Center technical crew and volunteers’ outstanding efforts, participants were able to attend plenary sessions from either the event main auditorium or a second hall with livestreaming capabilities to cater for the high participation that according to organizers reached 400+ delegates.

In a welcoming collegial atmosphere, attendees had the chance to get updates through a series of content-rich talks in the form of illustrative plenary presentations on a wide variety of topics covering

- open access national and international adoption rates,
- latest copyright legislation reforms,
- new cooperative initiatives design, implementation and impact facts and figures, namely H.E.LI.N economic libraries network, HAMLIC Hellenic Music Libraries Cooperative, ILSaS, AMELib Accessible Multimodal Electronic Library for the print-disabled users
- HEAL-link Office recent publisher agreements and services overview
- most current institutional repository system solutions,
- innovative information literacy delivery approaches
- conceptualization of synergistic librarian CPD solutions
- federated access related research and
- University of Macedonia and National Technical University of Athens libraries CSFs capitalization case studies.

Through a unique convergence of learning and networking, mix and mingle coffee / lunch breaks and gala conference dinner socializing and a rich mix of empirical research, case studies, conceptual analyses and stocktaking reporting, participants were provided with a good number of opportunities to exchange viewpoints on

- projects developments
- issues and challenges facing Greek Academic Librarianship today
- internal and external pressures that local stakeholders and new international communicational, technological and educational paradigms exert on the field
- new interventions and conceptualized solutions around CPD, extended librarian roles and collaboration prospects (e.g. GIS librarians, InfoLit, research evaluation)

Key Takeaways

Plenary talks Q&As in addition to closing session panel discussion wrap-up helped audience recall event highlights and briefly explore ways presentations' key points could be translated into meaningful interventions taking into account the overriding requirement of cooperative synergistic actions seen as the perfect approach to

- Dealing with the economic downturn impact on library budgets and staff shortcomings
- Designing and implementing successful new paradigm-driven projects
- Influencing national authorities in favor of according academic librarians a significant margin of initiative and appreciation, repositioning library at the heart of the institution and formalizing their already dynamic involvement in the Learning and Teaching process.

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